

Joint UPF and Application Placement in Multi-Slice Edge Networks: A Reinforcement Learning Strategy

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Abstract—The virtualization and softwarization of 5G/6G mobile networks have enabled the deployment and orchestration of cloud-native network and application functions. The deployment of these functions is crucial, as the placement of data plane elements (i.e., User Plane Function (UPF)) and vertical services can significantly impact the overall user latency. However, in multi-slice edge scenarios, characterized by users with distinct levels of criticality, the problem of UPF and application placement is becoming increasingly complex due to i) the various costs involved and ii) the limited computational resources at the edge. In this paper, the problem of joint UPF and application placement for a multi-slice user scenario is studied, taking into account multiple cost components that influence the placement decision, including service migration, traffic forwarding, server activation and processing costs. To tackle this problem, we introduce a Joint UPF and Application Reinforcement Learning-based (JUAP-RL) algorithm, which decides the UPF and application deployment location and coordinates the placement stages. Extensive experiments have shown that JUAP-RL demonstrates up to 17% gain in terms of user acceptance ratio and up to 23.4% reduction in provisioning cost compared to baseline schemes.

Index Terms—Network slicing, UPF placement, Application placement, Zero-touch Service Management, Edge Computing

I. INTRODUCTION

Network function virtualisation (NFV) and network slicing will be crucial for meeting the stringent requirements of 5G and beyond networks. On one hand, NFV facilitates the implementation of complex network functions as software components running on general purpose hardware [1]. Softwarised functions can easily be scaled-in/out and migrated according to the real-time network evolution [2]. On the other hand, network slicing facilitates the customized network configuration towards service-specific requirements. This flexibility enhances the potential of edge computing that extends computational resources closer to the data source, enabling the transition towards edge- and cloud-native scenarios, where the placement of various network functions can be tailored to meet specific service requirements [3].

As a core element of the 5G architecture, the User Plane Function (UPF) provides the necessary mechanisms to connect end-devices and data networks by ensuring efficient data routing, packet inspection and quality of service (QoS) enforcement [4]. Thanks to the softwarisation paradigm, the UPF can be implemented as a software packaged into either a virtual

machine or a container image, thus introducing flexibility regarding its instantiation and placement, allowing for meeting the requirements of different services and applications [5].

However, the distinctiveness among service applications with different criticality levels, in combination with the heterogeneity of edge-cloud nodes in terms of resource and latency performance, complicate the placement decision of cloud-native components (including UPF). In network slicing, where applications with distinct levels of criticality and QoS requirements are assigned to different slices [6] [7], the decisions about UPF and application placement to meet and prioritize the needs of more critical services becomes challenging. For instance, placing the UPF closer to the end users (e.g., at the edge nodes) reduces the traffic path length, thus satisfying latency requirements of critical services [8]. However, such nodes are resource constrained, something that limits the number of users that can be supported by a UPF deployed at such nodes. On the contrary, deploying the UPF at the cloud offers computational resource availability albeit at a non-acceptable latency performance for critical applications.

There is a number of works addressing the UPF placement problem focusing on dynamic UPF reconfiguration [5], [9]–[12], UPF scheduling [13] and joint UPF and traffic routing [8]. However, in real scenarios, the end-to-end delay is affected by the location of both the UPF and the application service. By placing both the UPF and the application closer to the user, the overall service access delay is reduced, while the delay increases if either the UPF or the application is placed far from the user. Moreover, in a practical cloud-native scenario, the number of UPF and application instances that can be deployed is limited due to the limited edge node resources and overhead costs related to energy consumption, software licensing, and hardware costs of server deployment, among others. Hence, the deployment of UPF or application instances in all regions/cells of the network is rendered prohibitive. In this way, a single UPF or application instance may need to be shared among users from different regions, further exacerbating the placement problem [13]. In cloud-native scenarios, sharing of an application instance among multiple geographically distributed users may also be imposed by the specific use case, such as those envisaged in 6G, including multi-player online gaming and holographic type communica-

tion, among others. In practice, the number of total requests and the number of requests per slice type is different and may be dynamic across these distributed cells, necessitating dynamic adaption of the placement solution. However, this can lead to additional cost overheads from service migration and server activation, on top of the resource-related ones, like transmission and processing costs. These cost components can be often conflicting, as decreasing one may result in an increase in another. For instance, minimizing server activation costs by utilizing an already active server might result in higher transmission costs and delay violations (e.g., in case the delay to the active server is prohibitive for delay-sensitive flows). This complexity intensifies the placement problem, as it becomes challenging to predict the effects of different cost components on the overall optimization problem.

Moreover, the placement decisions of the UPF and the application instances are tightly coupled, since their co-location on the same server eliminates the delay and link resource consumption overhead (costs that appear when they are deployed on different servers). However, if the UPF is initially placed on a resource-constrained server, it may be impractical to subsequently place the application on the same server due to these resource limitations. Therefore, the UPF and application should be placed in a coordinated manner to realise near-optimal global placement solutions. A first attempt towards this direction has been made in [14], where the authors tackle the problem of joint UPF and edge server placement. However, in their work, servers are placed in a static manner, while the edge servers and the UPF instances are deployed in two uncoordinated steps.

In this paper, we focus on the joint UPF and application placement problem in multi-slice edge scenarios with UPF sharing. Our main contribution is threefold:

- 1) We define and formulate the joint UPF and application placement decision for a multi-slice edge scenario as an integer linear programming (ILP) problem.
- 2) We introduce a Joint UPF and Application Reinforcement Learning-based (JUAP-RL) algorithm, targeting a cost-effective and resource-efficient coordinated deployment of UPF and application instances, taking into account various placement cost components, including service migration, traffic forwarding, server activation and processing costs.
- 3) We extensively evaluate the performance of JUAP-RL in various scenarios against baseline algorithms. The results demonstrate a higher user acceptance ratio and lower placement cost for JUAP-RL, through the prioritization of critical slice requests.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section II presents the system model and the problem formulation. The proposed JUAP-RL algorithm is described in Section III. The performance evaluation of JUAP-RL is presented in Section IV and the paper is concluded in Section V.

II. SYSTEM MODEL AND PROBLEM FORMULATION

In this section, we present the system model and a formulation of the dynamic joint UPF and service placement problem.

A. Network topology

The substrate network, depicted in Fig. 1, is composed of a set of base stations $\mathcal{B} = \{b_1, b_2, \dots, b_M\}$, a set of edge servers $\mathcal{E} = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_K\}$, and a set of interconnecting links (\mathcal{L}) between the different substrate nodes. Each base station $b \in \mathcal{B}$ covers a geographical area (cell) and hosts an edge server with probability b_{prob} . Each server $e \in \mathcal{E}$ is characterised by computational capacity v_e^{max} , activation cost C_e , and a processing cost for each unit of bandwidth γ_e^o . Each link $l \in \mathcal{L}$ is associated with bandwidth capacity B_l^{max} , delay D_l and a cost ζ_l for each unit of bandwidth consumed on this link.

Fig. 1. System Model

B. Service Model

We model each service request from a user as a flow $f \in \mathcal{F}$ belonging to a slice $j \in \mathcal{J}$, where \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{J} denote the sets of all flows and slices, respectively. We denote by $f_j \in \mathcal{F}_j$ a flow belonging to slice j , where \mathcal{F}_j is the set of all flows belonging to slice j . Each flow $f \in \mathcal{F}$ is associated with a slice type $j \in \mathcal{J}$, a migration cost ϕ_j^f , computational demand for UPF processing σ_u^f , computational demand for application processing σ_a^f , bandwidth demand B_{dem}^f , end-to-end delay requirement δ_j^f , and revenue per bandwidth unit λ_j^f .

Taking into account the limited edge resources, we assume that a single UPF (u) is shared among all flows from the different cells, while all flows of slice j access a single application instance β_j . Additionally, the binary variables $\chi_{u,e}^t \in \{0, 1\}$ and $\beta_{j,h}^t \in \{0, 1\}$ denote that u and β_j , respectively, is deployed on server $e \in \mathcal{E}$ at time instant $t \in \mathcal{T}$ (i.e., one if it is deployed and zero otherwise). Finally, we denote by $w_{f,l}^t \in \{0, 1\} = 1$ if $f \in \mathcal{F}$ traverses $l \in \mathcal{L}$. The system model parameters are summarized in Table I.

C. Problem Formulation

The joint UPF and application placement problem entails determining a feasible edge server to host the shared UPF u and each slice specific application instance β_j . Therefore, the problem is formulated as an ILP to maximize the revenue-to-cost ratio for each admitted flow on average as

$$\text{maximise : } \frac{1}{|\mathcal{F}_a|} \left(\frac{Rev_{tot}}{C_{tot}} \right) \quad (1)$$

TABLE I
NOTATION

Parameter	Description
B_l^{max}	Bandwidth capacity of link $l \in \mathcal{L}$
D_l	Delay on $l \in \mathcal{L}$
v_e^{max}	Computational capacity of node $e \in \mathcal{E}$
B_{dem}^f	Bandwidth demand of $f \in \mathcal{F}$
σ_u^f	Computational demand of f at UPF host
σ_i^f	Computational demand of f application host
C_e	Activation cost of $e \in \mathcal{E}$
δ_j^f	delay requirement of request $f \in \mathcal{F}_j$
$w_{f,l}^t \in \{0, 1\}$	$w_{f,l}^t=1$ if f traverses link $l \in \mathcal{L}$ at time t
ζ_l	Cost per bandwidth unit at $l \in \mathcal{L}$
$z_u^t \in \{0, 1\}$	$z_u^t=1$ if UPF u is migrated at time t
$z_j^t \in \{0, 1\}$	$z_j^t=1$ if β_j is migrated at time t
ϕ_j^f	Cost of migrating flow $f \in \mathcal{F}_j$
γ_e^f	Cost of processing flow f at server e
ζ_l	Forwarding cost per unit bandwidth on $l \in \mathcal{L}$
$\eta_{f,j}^t \in \{0, 1\}$	$\eta_{f,j}^t=1$ if $f \in \mathcal{F}_j$ is served at time t
$\chi_{u,e} \in \{0, 1\}$	$\chi_{u,e}=1$ if UPF is mapped on $e \in \mathcal{E}$ at t
$\beta_{j,e}^t \in \{0, 1\}$	$\beta_{j,e}^t=1$ if β_j is mapped on $e \in \mathcal{E}$ at t
$\zeta_e^t \in \{0, 1\}$	$\zeta_e^t=1$ if $e \in \mathcal{E}$ is active at time t
$y_e^t \in \{0, 1\}$	$y_e^t=1$ if $e \in \mathcal{E}$ is activated at t

$$C.1 \quad \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}} \sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}} \chi_{u,e}^t \sigma_u^f \eta_{f,j}^t + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}} \sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}} \beta_{j,e}^t \sigma_i^f \eta_{f,j}^t \leq v_e^{max} \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, e \in \mathcal{E} \quad (2)$$

$$C.2 \quad \sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}} \omega_{f,l}^t B_{dem}^f \leq B_l^{max} \quad \forall l \in \mathcal{L}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (3)$$

$$C.3 \quad \sum_{e \in \mathcal{E}} \chi_{u,e}^t \leq 1 \quad \forall e \in \mathcal{E} \quad (4)$$

$$C.4 \quad \sum_{e \in \mathcal{E}} \beta_{j,e}^t \leq 1 \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{J}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (5)$$

$$C.5 \quad \sum_{l \in \mathcal{L}} \omega_{f,l}^t D_l \leq \delta_j^f \quad \forall f \in \mathcal{F}, t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (6)$$

where \mathcal{F}_a , Rev_{tot} and C_{tot} denote the set of served flows, total revenue and cost associated with the served flows, respectively. Constraints $C.1$ and $C.2$ relate to server computational and link bandwidth resources, respectively. $C.3$ and $C.4$ constrain the UPF and a slice-specific application instance to be deployed on a single node at a given time and $C.5$ is the end-to-end delay constraint.

The total revenue Rev_{tot} is defined as

$$Rev_{tot} = \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}} \sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}} \eta_{f,j}^t \lambda_j^f B_{dem}^f, \quad (7)$$

where $\eta_{f,j}^t = 1$ if flow f is served at time t . The provisioning cost can be estimated as

$$C_{tot} = C_{proc} + C_{fwd} + C_{mig} + C_{activ}, \quad (8)$$

where C_{proc} , C_{fwd} , C_{mig} , C_{activ} denote the processing, forwarding, migration and server activation cost, respectively.

The processing cost aggregates the processing cost at the UPF and application instance host node(s) as

$$C_{proc} = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}} \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}, f \in \mathcal{F}} \chi_{u,e}^t \gamma_e^f \eta_{f,j}^t + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}} \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}, f \in \mathcal{F}} \beta_{j,e}^t \gamma_e^f \eta_{f,j}^t, \quad (9)$$

where γ_e^f is the cost of processing flow f at node e . We consider γ_e^f to be directly proportional to the bandwidth requirement of each flow as $\gamma_e^f = \gamma_o^e \times B_{dem}^f$, where γ_o^e denotes the processing cost from each unit bandwidth processed at e .

The migration cost is related to the migration of the UPF or the application instance supporting a flow and is calculated as

$$C_{mig} = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}} \sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}, t \in \mathcal{T}} \eta_{f,j}^t z_u^t \phi_j^f + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}} \sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}, t \in \mathcal{T}} \eta_{f,j}^t z_j^t \phi_j^f, \quad (10)$$

The node activation cost is related to activation of a server to host a UPF or application instance and is evaluated as

$$C_{activ} = \sum_{e \in \mathcal{E} | \zeta_e^t = 1} y_e^t C_e. \quad (11)$$

The forwarding cost relates to the bandwidth consumption along the edges traversed by the traffic from the source base station to the application server host and is evaluated as

$$C_{fwd} = \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}, f \in \mathcal{F}} \sum_{l \in \mathcal{L}} \omega_{f,l}^t B_{dem}^f \zeta_l. \quad (12)$$

III. JOINT UPF AND APPLICATION REINFORCEMENT LEARNING-BASED ALGORITHM (JUAP-RL)

Obtaining an optimal placement solution for Eq. (1) requires enumerating multiple permutations of hosts for UPF and application hosting, rendering exact approaches infeasible for delay-sensitive slices. This motivates the use of an RL approach capable of executing in polynomial time with high performance gain due to its capability to infer the effects of the different cost components on the optimization problem, compared to heuristic approaches.

A. MDP model for JUAP-RL

We consider the system to be fully observable by an RL agent, hence we model the system as a Markovian Decision Process (MDP) defined by the tuple (S_t, A_t, P_t, R_t) , where S_t denotes the system state set; A_t denotes the set of possible discrete actions, related to the UPF and application placement; P_t denotes the transition probabilities between states and R_t denotes the obtained reward after each state transition. The considered parameters of the MDP tuple are discussed below:

1) *State space*: The system state is modelled as an $|\mathcal{N}_h| \times K$ feature matrix, where $|\mathcal{N}_h|$ and K denote the number of host servers and the number of features associated with each server, respectively. The extracted features for each server are: the residual CPU, the average distance to all base stations weighted by the traffic distribution per slice type at each base station, the average bandwidth to different base stations, server active status $\in \{0, 1\}$, and the unit processing cost.

2) *Reward*: For each decision epoch, the reward is obtained as the received revenue-to-cost ratio, thus maximising the reward results in optimising the deployment objective (Eq. (1)).

3) *Action Space*: The action space at each decision step is a vector of size N_h+1 where N_h is the number of host servers. The additional index corresponds to a scenario where no host is selected for hosting the UPF or the application.

B. Policy network architecture and training

JUAP-RL relies on a policy network constituted of four main layers: 1) the input layer, which receives as input the state feature matrix; 2) a convolutional layer, which performs a convolution between feature matrix and the internal weights of the layer; 3) a softmax layer, which transforms the convolutional layer output into a vector of probabilities, reflecting the suitability of each node to host either the UPF or an application instance; 4) a filtering layer added to avoid selection of infeasible hosts.

During training, the policy network outputs a probability distribution over the different server hosts to be chosen for mapping the UPF or application instances. The complete policy network decision is divided into $M = |\mathcal{J}| + 1$ decision steps involving selection of a host(s) for: 1) the shared UPF, and 2) the application instance of each slice group in \mathcal{J} . The above decision steps are tightly correlated, since a poor decision at a given step has an impact on subsequent steps. In this way, to ensure coordinated mapping of the UPF and application instances, during the training phase, a decision sequence is considered to be successful once all the above steps are successful. This constraint is however relaxed at the testing stage since, in principle, it is possible to accept some slices while rejecting others. At the end of the decision sequence, a reward is calculated which is used to calculate the gradients of all the internal weights of the neural network applying back propagation.

Although our proposed approach is applicable to any number of slices, for training of the policy network and performance evaluation of JUAP-RL, we considered flows belonging to two slices (critical and non-critical), hence $|\mathcal{J}| = 2$ and $M = 3$ with the rest of the parameters adopted as shown in Table II. The critical slice flows are associated with a higher revenue, albeit with more strict latency requirements and service interruption costs compared to non-critical slice flows. The training results are shown in Fig. 2. Fig. 2(a) shows that the policy network learns the optimal policy amidst changing states by maximising the reward with an increase in training epochs. Moreover, in Figs. 2(b) and 2(c), we can see that the policy network learns to prioritise admission of critical slices over non-critical slices.

IV. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

The simulation settings, benchmark algorithms and performance evaluation of JUAP-RL are discussed in this section.

A. Simulation settings

We assume a network topology (similar to our system model in Fig. 1) with 11 base stations. The values of the

different simulation parameters (unless otherwise stated) for the requests and network are shown in Table II. Note that $U(x, y)$ in the table denotes the uniform distribution between x and y .

TABLE II
SIMULATION PARAMETERS

Param.	description	Value
j	critical/non-critical slice group index	1/2
$ \mathcal{J} $	Number of slices	2
$ \mathcal{N}_b $	Number of base stations (BS))	11
b_{prob}	BS server host probability	0.8
v_e^{max}	Server computational capacity (vCPU)	$U(100, 400)$
B_{dem}^f	Bandwidth demand per flow (Mb/s)	$U(0.5, 2)$
B_{max}^f	Link bandwidth capacity (Gb/s)	$U(1, 5)$
ϕ_1^f	Migration cost, critical slice flow (\$)	1
ϕ_2^f	Migration cost, non-critical slice flow (\$)	0.5
δ_1^f	Delay requirement for Critical slice (ms)	$U(2, 5)$
δ_2^f	Delay req. for non-critical slice (ms)	$U(5, 10)$
λ_1^f	Critical slice revenue for each Mb/s (\$)	$U(10, 40)$
λ_2^f	Non-critical slice revenue for each Mb/s(\$)	$U(1, 5)$
σ_u^f, σ_i^f	Computational demand per flow (vCPU)	$U(0.01, 0.5)$
ζ_i	Transmission cost per unit bw (\$)	$U(5, 13)$
γ_e^o	Processing cost per unit bW (\$)	$U(1, 10)$

B. Benchmark algorithms

The adopted baseline algorithms are presented below:

1) *Bandwidth Greedy Algorithm (BWGA)*: For UPF placement, *BWGA* selects the server with the lowest number of hops to all traffic sources. Then, for placement of the application, the server closest to the chosen UPF host is chosen, thus minimising the number of hops traversed by the data traffic. Thus *BWGA* greedily minimises bandwidth consumption, reducing request rejection due to bandwidth bottlenecks and delay.

2) *Load balance-based algorithm (LB)*: For each decision step regarding the placement of either the UPF or service application instances, *LB* ranks all candidate hosts according to their residual resource score, calculated as the product of the host's residual CPU by the accumulative residual bandwidth of the host's inbound links. Then, the host with the highest score is selected for hosting the current function (i.e., UPF or application instance). In this way, *LB* minimizes server and link resource bottlenecks, guaranteeing a good long-term acceptance ratio performance and, hence, revenue.

3) *Greedy processing algorithm (G-proc)*: For each decision step, *G-proc* ranks all candidate hosts according to their processing costs and the hosts with the lowest processing cost are selected to host the different functions at each stage, targeting to minimise processing costs, node activation cost and migration cost for a fixed network topology.

C. Simulation results and discussion

In the results of Fig. 3, the total number of flows at each BS is varied from 50 to 1000. The number of critical slice flows are randomly generated between 0 and the number of

Fig. 2. Results of training step of the policy neural network

Fig. 3. Results for varying number of flows across base stations

Fig. 4. Results for different critical slice generation probabilities

flows at the BS, the remainder being the non-critical slice flows. From Fig. 3(a), JUAP-RL yields up to a 17.2% gain in terms of acceptance ratio (AR) with an average value of 42.4% followed by *LB*, *BWGA*, and *G-Proc* with average values of 35.2%, 31.2%, and 26.13%, respectively. This is attributed to the ability of JUAP-RL to infer the long-term effects of the different attributes, i.e., CPU, bandwidth consumption and link delay constraints, while making the placement decision. Moreover, JUAP-RL coordinates the mapping of the UPF and application instances resulting in better placement solutions. *LB* yields good results with respect to other greedy approaches, especially with increase in demand size due to its

load balancing capability that minimises flow rejections due to node and link resource bottlenecks. Since, *BWGA* relies on shortest path nodes, which are fixed for a fixed network topology, its performance degrades with demand size due to link bottlenecks. *G-proc* results in the worst performance since the nodes associated with low processing costs may be far from the traffic sources resulting in high link resource consumption and delay, hence request rejection due to delay constraints and bandwidth bottlenecks.

Regarding the acceptance ratio of critical slice flows, from Fig. 3(b), JUAP-RL achieves an AR value of 21.2% compared to 19.2%, 15.86%, 14.13% attained by *BWGA*, *LB* and

G-proc, respectively. With low demand size values, *BWGA* demonstrates a superior performance over all algorithms, since it greedily targets lower delay, hence, being able to admit delay stringent critical slices. However, with increase in number of requests, its performance significantly degrades with respect to JUAP-RL, since it fails to admit requests due to link resource bottlenecks. For the considered scenario, *BWGA* offers better AR performance for critical slice compared to *LB*, although *LB* performs better with increase in number of requests. The *G-proc* results in the worst performance due to delay violations of critical slices.

From Fig. 3(c), for low demand size, *BWGA* demonstrates a better performance, since it admits more critical slice flows than other algorithms for this demand size (as discussed also above). These critical slice flows are associated with higher revenue and low transmission costs due to their low delay requirements, hence a higher revenue-to-cost ratio per admitted request. However, this performance degrades with the increase in request number due to resource bottlenecks forcing flows to traverse longer paths and nodes of higher processing cost. On average, JUAP-RL achieves the best performance across all demand sizes with an average value of 0.38, followed by *BWGA*, *G-Proc* and *LB* with average values of 0.34, 0.27 and 0.25, respectively. In Fig. 3(d), we can see that the placement cost for all algorithms increases with the number of flows per BS, mainly due to the increased resource costs. However, JUAP-RL results in the lowest cost with an average value of 69.57, translating in a 20% gain compared to the best baseline *LB*, whose total cost is 87.5. *BWGA* and *G-Proc* result in a cost of 99.2 and 126.4 respectively.

The impact of the number of critical flows is analysed in the results of Fig. 4, where the probability of critical slice flows is varied from 0.1 to 0.9, fixing the number of flows at each base station at 400. Fig. 4(a) shows that the total acceptance ratio of all the algorithms tends to decrease as the number of critical slice flows increases, since they fail to satisfy the strict latency requirements of critical slice flows. JUAP-RL results in the highest total AR, with an average value of 47.6% across all probabilities which is a 14% gain over the best baseline *LB*, whose average AR is 40.1%. *G-Proc* and *BWGA* AR values are 20.3% and 34.5%, respectively. Moreover, JUAP-RL results in the highest number of critical slice flows with an average critical flow AR value of 24.5%, translating in a 22% gain compared to the best baseline schemes *LB* and *BWGA*, whose average value are 19% and 18%, respectively. *G-proc* results in the worst performance with an AR value of 10.6%. Similarly, in Fig. 4(c), JUAP-RL results in up to a 20% gain over the best baselines in terms of revenue-to-cost ratio with an average value of 0.43. The average values for *BWGA*, *LB*, and *G-proc* are 0.34, 0.31 and 0.17, respectively.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper has addressed the problem of joint UPF and application placement considering a multi-slice edge scenario

under multiple conflicting cost components, including: service migration, traffic forwarding, server activation and processing costs. We introduced JUAP-RL, an RL-based algorithm, to solve the formulated problem with the obtained results demonstrating that JUAP-RL results in up to a 17% and 23.4% improvement in terms of acceptance ratio and provisioning cost, respectively, compared to a set of greedy baseline algorithms. JUAP-RL coordinates the mapping of both the UPF and application instance and is found to prioritise admission of critical slices, rendering it well suited in multi-priority service orchestration scenarios. The future work will explore a scenario involving joint deployment of multiple instances of UPFs and applications for each slice type.

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